

Say what you want and the universe will respond

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A long time ago, I heard someone say: “When someone tells you a book changed their life, go read that book.” This simple advice stuck with me, and I keep following it ever since. Recently, a friend who had just secured a scholarship for his Ph.D. in Australia shared on his Facebook post how a single book transformed his life. He admitted that he was once a procrastinator and self-doubt, but this book helped him break free from those habits and achieved a lot of success. Going through his achievements during the last three years, I was impressed and sold. And that book, *Key to Living the Law of Attraction* by Jack Canfield and D.D. Watkins [1].

You can tell exactly what I do next. I immediately ordered a physical copy of the book. Something about holding a real book, feeling it's in my hand, its smell (I love the smell of a new book), sitting in a quiet corner forgetting about time and space, and emerging myself in those pages creates a joyful experience and connection for me. Perhaps this stems from my love for not just reading but also owning books. However, it isn't just personal preference—research shows that the favor and attachment to physical books over e-books is a sign of avid readers and a passion for reading [2,3].

Anyway, as I read that book, one core message stood out and I summarized it as “when you know what you want and open yourself to opportunities, you create a high frequency vibration that resonates with those opportunities, the universe will respond to you.” The authors explained that this happens because you start noticing people, resources, and ideas that were always present but filtered out by your mind. The word “filter out” is a light bulb moment for me, connecting my thoughts to the *Mindsponge Theory* [4] and all of my personal experiences.

The Mindsponge Theory posits that the human mind is like a sponge. It absorbs and rejects information based on core beliefs [4]. For example, if I believe, “I’ll never get a fellowship,” I might subconsciously reject opportunities or fail to notice them. Even though fellowship announcements are all around me, my mind filters them out, reinforcing my belief that I’ll never succeed. This self-fulfilling prophecy is a cognitive bias that the Mindsponge Theory captures effectively. By consciously and subconsciously altering our beliefs (Canfield and Watkins suggest using affirmation to alter subconscious thinking), we can reshape what our minds absorb, thereby attracting or letting opportunities come to us.

Reflecting on this connection excited me because while Canfield and Watkins emphasize the power of belief (the law of attraction), they fall short on explaining the scientific mechanisms behind this phenomenon. The Mindsponge Theory provides that missing link. It not only supports the idea that beliefs shape perceptions and opportunities, but also grounds this in a cognitive, psychological, and social framework.

For me, this realization also affirms a lifelong philosophy: If you want something badly enough and work toward it, the universe—or rather, your own mind—will align resources in your favour. This principle has guided my journey, from working as a field researcher in Vietnam to a Ph.D. candidate in the United States. In every step of this journey, through each project [5,6,7,8,9], I have always received support, resources, and opportunities that I once thought magical.

So, for my future self and anyone pursuing goals, remember: The law of attraction is not just philosophy; it has scientific underpinnings. By aligning your beliefs and actions, you can transform your life. Whether through the lens of attraction or the Mindsponge Theory, the message is clear—what you focus on becomes your reality.

References

- [1] Canfield, J., & Watkins, D. D. (2007). *Jack Canfield’s key to living the law of attraction : a simple guide to creating the life of your dreams*. Health Communications, Inc.
- [2] Waheed, M., Kaur, K., Ain, N., & Sanni, S. A. (2015). Emotional attachment and multidimensional self-efficacy: extension of innovation diffusion theory in the context of eBook reader. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 34(12), 1147–1159. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144929x.2015.1004648>
- [3] Spence, C. (2020). The Multisensory Experience of Handling and Reading Books. *Multisensory Research*, 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1163/22134808-bja10015>
- [4] Vuong, Q.-H. (2022). Mindsponge Theory. *Sciendo EBooks*. <https://doi.org/10.2478/9788367405157>
- [5] Tran, T. M. A., Ko, D. W., Park, C. R., & Le, H. D. (2019). A bayesian network analysis of reforestation decisions by rural mountain communities in Vietnam. *Forest Science and Technology*, 15(2), 51–57. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21580103.2019.1581665>

- [6] Hai Dinh Le, Thi, T., Hai, T., Luu Thi Van, & Ngo Thi Mai. (2024). Analyzing determinants of long-rotation plantation decisions by local households in Quang Tri Province, Vietnam with Bayesian Networks. *Land Use Policy*, 138, 107029–107029. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2023.107029>
- [7] Tran, T. M. A., Gagnon, V. S., & Schelly, C. (2024). A review of traditional ecological knowledge in resilient livelihoods and forest ecosystems: lessons for restoration sciences and practices. *Forests, Trees and Livelihoods*, 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14728028.2024.2408725>
- [8] Mai, T., Reed-VanDam, C., Belopavlovich, K., Brown, E., Higdon, K., Lane-Clark, S. N., McGowen, K. M., Shaw, E., & Gagnon, V. (2024). Decentering humans in sustainability: a framework for Earth-centered kinship and practice. *Socio-Ecological Practice Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42532-024-00206-9>
- [9] Nguyễn Văn Thị, Anh, M., Nguyễn Thị Hà, Phùng Văn Khoa, & Vũ Tiến Thịnh. (2016). Ứng dụng GIS và viễn thám trong quản lý chi trả dịch vụ môi trường rừng tại lưu vực thủy điện Hương Sơn, Hà Tĩnh. *Tạp chí Khoa học và Công nghệ Lâm nghiệp*, 6(6), 092-100. <https://journal.vnuf.edu.vn/vi/article/view/1133>